

Intensified Multi-stage Constructed Wetland to valorise anaerobic digestate centrate

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Abstract

An innovative multi-stage Constructed Wetland (CW) has been developed to treat anaerobic digestate centrate with ammonium and phosphorus removal efficiencies among 84-95% and 96-99%, respectively, with a high presence of nitrifying archaea. In addition, the nitrified stream allows its valorisation as a potential nitrate/nitrite source to turn more sustainable anoxic biogas biodesulphurisation processes.

Keywords (maximum 6 in alphabetical order)

Anoxic biogas desulphurisation; Digestate centrate; Drinking water treatment sludge; Nitrification; Microbial N-cycle diversity; Multi-stage Constructed Wetland.

INTRODUCTION

Constructed Wetlands (CWs) represent an efficient eco-technological conglomerate interweaving water security, energy possibility and environmental protection (Kataki et al., 2021). These natural treatment systems are a sustainable and viable option for the treatment of domestic and urban wastewater. However, further research on their application to more complex wastewater, such as anaerobic digestate centrate, is required to expand their application niche. To overcome emerging phosphorus (P) and nitrogen removal challenges and to reduce surface area requirements, new designs and operational strategies have been developed to intensify CWs (Dotro et al., 2017).

The combination of two intensification strategies, the use of drinking water treatment sludge (DWTS) as reactive substrate (Hernández-Crespo et al., 2022, 2024) and the operation based on tidal flow mode, has already been successfully evaluated for the treatment of animal farm wastewater (Zhao et al., 2011). Herein, a multi-stage CW using these two intensification strategies has been investigated to achieve simultaneous removal of ammonium (NH_4^+) and P from centrate, to provide an alternative nitrified stream to be used as electron and nutrient source during anoxic biogas biodesulphurisation (Sempere et al., 2022) and to reduce the pollutant load returned to Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) headworks.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

System description and operating conditions

The pilot plant consisted of two independent multi-stage CWs referred to as gravel and DWTS, respectively, according to their main substrate. Both systems are identical in terms of configuration and operation: flow type, treated volume, number of cycles per day and contact time (Tc). Each one is composed by 3 stages connected in series (Figure 1). The first one consists in three parallel “Tidal Flow” CWs operating alternatively treating centrate 2 days and resting 4. The second stage is

composed of two Vertical Flow CWs operating in parallel and their effluents are mixed and discharged by gravity into the third stage, which is composed of a Horizontal Subsurface CW. Both systems were planted with *Phragmites Australis*. Different operational strategies, number of cycles per day (2, 4 and 6) and Tc (30, 15, 5), were tested during 16 months.

Figure 1 Diagram of the multi-stage CW pilot plant configuration.

Measurements and analytical methods

Samples of influent and effluent streams from each stage and each system were collected 3 times per week for physic-chemical analysis. Water quality variables analysed, and methods (in parenthesis), were: ammonium (N-NH_4^+) (Hach test: ISO 7150-1), nitrites (N-NO_2^-) (Hach test: ISO 26777), nitrates (N-NO_3^-) (Hach test: ISO 7890-1-2), and total phosphorus (TP) (Hach test: digestion + ISO 6878). DNA was extracted from sediment using the EZNA Soil DNA Isolation Kit (Omega Bio-Tek). The V4 region of the 16S rRNA gene was sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq following Picazo et al. (2019). Sequences were processed using a UPARSE-based pipeline, with a chimera removal (UCHIME), and ZOTU cluste-ring (100% identity). Taxonomic assignment was performed using SILVA 138.1 database, excluding non-bacterial or archaeal sequences, then final ZOTU table was rarefied for downstream analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DWTS system showed a higher NH_4^+ removal capacity during the whole monitoring period. Average NH_4^+ -N concentrations were reduced through this system from 453 to 21 mgN/L, 504 to 58 mgN/L and 438 to 68 mgN/L, operating under 2, 4 and 6 cycles/day and with a TC of 30 min (Figure 2). The effluent obtained showed average NO_3^- -N concentrations of 412, 455 and 255 mgN/L, respectively, being the average inlet concentration as low as 2 mg/L. The results show that the nitrification process occurred at high rates in DWTS system, obtaining an ideal nitrified stream to be valorised in anoxic biogas biodesulphurisation. This high nitrification yield, compared with those achieved in the gravel system (29-53% NH_4^+ removal efficiencies), could be associated with a high adsorption capacity of the substrate (Peng et al. 2020) during the flooded period, and higher levels of microbial diversity of N-cycle-associated microorganisms. In fact, ammonia oxidising archaea (AOA) had a significantly greater development in the DWTS units (Figure 3), being almost negligible in gravel units.

When cycles per day were increased, the Average NH_4^+ -N removal efficiencies decreased slightly (from 95 to 84), this could be due to a reduction of the resting time, according to Hu et al. (2012).

Figure 2. $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ concentrations (mg/L) measured at the influent end effluents from the CW pilot systems. Dotted vertical lines represent the operational changes: a) 2 cycles/day, $T_c=30$ min.; b) 4 cycles/day, $T_c=30$ min.; c) 6 cycles/day, $T_c=30$ min.; d) 6 cycles/day, $T_c=15$ min.; e) 6 cycles/day, $T_c=5$ min.; f) 4 cycles/day, $T_c=15$ min.; g) 4 cycles/day, $T_c=5$ min.

An increase of $\text{NO}_2^-\text{-N}$ concentrations were observed at the outlet of each treatment stage when the cycles per day were increased, representing 1%, 5%, 24% of dissolved inorganic nitrogen measured at the outlet of the DWTS system at 2, 4, 6 cycles/day, respectively. This progressive increase could also be related with a lower reaeration capacity of the substrate due to the reduction of resting time. Regarding P removal, the DWTS system reached significantly higher removal efficiencies (96-99%) than the gravel system (26-46%), obtaining an average total P concentration of 0.5 mg/L at the outlet stream. This high P removal capacity is in accordance with previous studies treating effluents from secondary treatments in WWTPs (Hernandez-Crespo et al. 2022, 2024). Furthermore, P removal was stable regardless of the operational conditions applied.

Figure 3. Boxplots showing the abundance of nitrogen-cycle-related microbial groups based on normalised Illumina sequencing reads. In the plots, the boxes represent the interquartile range (IQR, 25th–75th percentiles), whiskers extend up to 1.5 times the IQR, and the solid line represents the median. The unfilled square indicates the mean.

CONCLUSIONS

The intensified Multi-stage CW has shown to be feasible treating centrate, allowing to reduce the pollutant load returned to WWTP headworks. The DWTS system has shown both nitrification capacity (NH_4^+ removal efficiency > 84%) and phosphorus removal efficiencies (> 96%) higher than those reached using a conventional substrate (<53% and <46%, respectively). Furthermore, the nitrates production achieved demonstrates that the innovative multi-stage CW developed is an efficient and low-cost technology which can be used to supply a nitrified stream for the anoxic biogas biodesulphurisation process, making it more sustainable.

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